

Improving landslide detection on SAR data through Deep Learning

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Abstract— In this letter, we use deep-learning convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to compare the landslide mapping and classification performances of optical images (from Sentinel-2) and SAR images (from Sentinel-1). The training, validation and test zones used to independently evaluate the performance of the CNN on different datasets are located in the eastern Iburi subprefecture in Hokkaido, where, at 03.08 local time (JST) on September 6, 2018, an Mw 6.6 earthquake triggered about 8000 coseismic landslides. We analyzed the conditions before and after the earthquake exploiting multi-polarization SAR as well as optical data by means of a CNN implemented in TensorFlow that points out the locations where the Landslide class is predicted as more likely. As expected, the CNN run on optical images proved itself excellent for the landslide detection task, achieving an overall accuracy of 98.96% while CNNs based on the combination of ground range detected (GRD) SAR data reached overall accuracies beyond 95%. Our findings show that the integrated use of SAR data may also allow for rapid detection even during storms and under dense cloud cover and provides comparable accuracy to classical optical change detection in landslide recognition and detection.

Index Terms— Landslides · deep learning (DL) · convolution neural networks(CNNs) · image classification · remote sensing (RS) · Sentinel-1 · Sentinel-2 · landslide detection · synthetic aperture radar (SAR) · TensorFlow.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the world, several natural phenomena, like earthquakes and intense rainfalls, sometimes combined with windstorms, can trigger multiple landslide events that can occur in groups of hundreds or even thousands in a region [1]–[5]. Those events can cause noticeable damages to natural and human infrastructures and can cause physical damages and heavy economic and social impacts [6]. Therefore, there is a growing need to intervene quickly and efficiently in the affected areas. Numerous techniques have been elaborate to produce susceptibility maps [7], and mitigation strategies [8], [9]. Undoubtedly, in the case of multiple occurrences of landslides over a large area, the most common mapping method relies on remote sensing data because of its potential to quickly mapping geological features of whole regions, without physical contact with the areas investigated. A vast amount of existing research has been performed to this end with knowledge-based methods, multiple regression, analytic hierarchy process [10], and

machine learning (ML) techniques [11]. However, as time is a key factor when mapping natural disaster effects [12], usage of optical data alone can have serious limitations in presence of cloud cover. A possible solution, offered by the usage of SAR satellites, has been exploited only scantily, so far, because landslide mapping algorithms have been mainly developed to run on optical data together with ancillary geological and topographic stationary information. Furthermore, SAR data requires specific analysis methods and classification algorithms, not yet fully developed for mass movements on natural slopes. Therefore, a research gap is still present in the lack of reliable image analysis methods to extract landslide mapping information from SAR images. Furthermore, an automatic method that employs the combination of CNNs and SAR data to extract spatial landslide information is not yet available. This is probably due to the characteristics of the SAR data, which provide different information as compared to optical data, making it essential the development of innovative techniques. Recently, deep learning (DL) and, mainly, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been used in various remote sensing tasks on VHR imagery, such as classification, segmentation [13], and object detection [14]. Nevertheless, a few are the studies that use CNNs for landslide detection. Ghorbanzadeh et al. [15] evaluated various ML algorithms on VHR optical data from the Rapid Eye satellite and topographic factors achieving 78.26% mIOU for a small window-size CNN. Another interesting study was carried out by Catani [16], in which the author evaluates different state-of-art CNNs on non-nadir and crowdsourced optical images of landslides to classify them, achieving overall accuracies between 87% and 90%. However, optical images may present limitations due to the cloud cover that are recurrent in most tropical areas as well as during storm-induced landslide activations everywhere, [17]. In some cases, the first cloudless image available in the service after multiple landslide events occurred about a month later, as happened in Nepal in 2015 [18], in Ecuador in 2016, and in Chile in December 2017. Despite the numerous methods and techniques that have been applied to SAR data to detect landslides [19], our study is the first that provides, to this end, a DL-based method employing the combination of CNNs and SAR data. Furthermore, the

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TABLE I
DATES OF ACQUISITION OF SENTINEL-2 AND SENTINEL-1 FOR THE STUDY
AREA IN HOKKAIDO 2018

Region and Year	Sentinel-2	Sentinel-1
Iburi, Hokkaido 2018	20-10	01-09 13-09 25-09

accuracy achieved is comparable to optical data performance. In the remainder of this letter, we show and discuss a deep-learning-based method to detect landslides also in case of illumination or atmospheric conditions not favorable for landform mapping. We apply CNN methods to landslide detection based on ground range detected (GRD) SAR imagery from the Sentinel-1 satellite, which, in a study carried out by Mondini et al. [20], showed unambiguous changes of amplitude caused by landslides in about eighty-four percent of the cases. Lastly, we compare the results obtained on eight different SAR-based datasets with an RGB dataset, and we provide the mapping of the study area by using the best models.

A. Study Area

Our case study area lies in the Iburi sub-prefecture of Hokkaido, Japan. It comprehends the Atsuma, Mukawa, and Abira towns, which present a specific population of less than 10,000 and a low population density of 17 inhabitants/km². The morphology of the area is composed mainly of hills. The maximum height is fewer than 800 m while the average elevation is 160 m. The basement complex of the region is mainly composed of sedimentary rocks of the Neogene tertiary system: layers of sandstone and mudstone, sandstone, conglomerate, and diatomaceous siltstone [21], [22]. In the study area, at 03.08 local time (JST) on September 6, 2018, struck an Mw 6.56 earthquake (HEIE). It was activated by a rupture of a low-activity blind fault with the epicenter located at 42.690 N 142.007 E [23]. The event triggered about 7837 coseismic landslides most of which occurred in locations where the elevation is less than 300 m [4]. The majority of the landslides slid down over the air-fall pumice and ash layers are shallow and are classified as planar type and spoon type [24].

B. Materials

The Sentinel-1 mission encompasses two polar-orbiting satellites that perform C-band synthetic aperture radar imaging while the Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission comprises two polar-orbiting satellites that sample 13 spectral bands: four bands at 10 m, six bands at 20 m, and three bands at 60 m spatial resolution. We downloaded Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images from the Copernicus Open Access Hub [25]. The first images (5 x 20 m) were acquired in Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) mode, with VV and VH polarization, and Interferometric Wide (IW) acquisition mode. GRD products are focused SAR data that has been detected, multi-looked, and projected to ground range using an Earth ellipsoid model [26]. Images were acquired from three different days: a) 01 September 2018, b) 13 September 2018, c) 25 September 2018. Lastly, a Sentinel-2 VHR RGB image (10 x 10 m) was obtained from the first cloud-free day after the multiple landslide event

TABLE II
COMPOSITE IMAGES CREATED WITH CORRESPONDING DATASET NAME

Dataset Name	Band 1	Band 2	Band 3
RGB	Red	Green	Blue
SSD	VV post-event	VH post-event	DEM
SSS	VV post-event	VH post-event	Slope
BAD	VV pre-event	VV post-event	DEM
BAS	VV pre-event	VV post-event	Slope
HHH	VH pre-event	VH post-event	VH post-event
BAA	VV pre-event	VV post-event	VV post-event
BAC	VV pre-event	VV post-event	VV post-event – VV pre-event
BAH	VV pre-event	VV post-event	VH post-event

(20 October 2018). Surface topography is one of the most influential elements regarding landslides in hilly and mountainous areas and, above all, the slope angle is considered an essential component of slope stability analysis [27]. Therefore, in this study, we used a 30 m resolution digital elevation model (DEM) acquired from USGS Earth Explorer [28] and slope angle to evaluate their impact on the SAR data. Table II shows all the band combination evaluated. Moreover, we experimented with both VV and VH amplitudes to create bi-temporal images with more than 4 bands without seeing an improvement in terms of model performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

The radar information from Sentinel-1 is exploited in combination with topographic factors, to evaluate the performance of a CNN to detect landslides. The workflow of this study is as follow:

- Designing nine different datasets, one composed of RGB images, four composed by SAR data and a topographic factor as third band, of which two with slope and two with DEM, and four constituted only by SAR data.
- Training the CNN on each training dataset and validating the performance on the corresponding test dataset sampled in the study area.
- Visualizing the predictions of the best models on an independent test area.

In the following sections, we give a description and the results of this workflow. Additional information and considerations are provided in the conclusion section.

A. Dataset Pool

To create the datasets, each of the composite images in Table II is sampled in the GIS environment using the 'Export training data for deep learning' tool, that, after designing numerous polygons on known landslides, samples various clips per polygon with a predefined shape, stride, and resolution. The polygons' position is chosen, by using the support of an accurate inventory of 7837 co-seismic landslides based on the interpretation of the PlanetScope images [4] and concerning the high variability of both classes, being careful to include various landslide shapes, orientations, and dimensions. To shape the the *positive* class, we supervise the sampling on the RGB imagery (polygon positions according to the patches sampled) so that the percentage of landslide pixel in the patches

TABLE III
NUMBER OF PATCHES FOR TRAINING VALIDATION AND TEST SETS

Training		Test		Validation	
POS	NEG	POS	NEG	POS	NEG
711	707	99	492	249	411

is enough for being easily recognized from the algorithm. Therefore, a sample with at least one pixel is not always taken as positive. As for the *negative* class, no landslide pixels are contained in the patches. We include different land covers, such as urban, wooded, and agricultural areas. In some patches can be casually present more than one land cover. In all the datasets, the spatial resolution of the images is 25 x 25 pixels, which is equivalent to a spatial extension of 250 x 250 m for optical RGB images and 125 x 420 m for SAR products. We select this image size as the best size based on a cross-validation for our study area. Training, validation, and test sets are sampled geographically separated, from different sectors/locations of the study area, to avoid overlapping between patches.

B. Supervised Classification

To Recently, deep-learning methods and, above all, CNNs have accomplished reliable results in various tasks in computer vision, proving to be the state-of-art of this field [29]. A CNN can autonomously learn hierarchical feature representations of an image, enabling it to perform classification tasks directly from images, e.g., recognizing a specific image without using human-designed features [30]. The peculiarity of a CNN is its architecture, which is composed of a variable number of so-called hidden layers that exercise convolutional and pooling operations. During the training process, an input image flows through the network that scans it with a set of trainable kernels, resulting in a group of feature maps (forward phase), then gradients are backpropagated, and parameters are updated (backward phase). The output of each convolutional layer is filtered by an activation function (e.g., sigmoid, ReLU, Softmax, hyperbolic tangent) that performs non-linear transformations [31]. The pooling layer, usually placed after the convolutional layer, aims to simplify the output by performing non-linear down-sampling to reduce the parameters. In this letter, we modify a network provided by the TensorFlow Core *Image Classification* library. The model consists of three convolution blocks of 3x3 filters with a max pooling layer in each of them. Dropout and connected layer are activated by a ReLU activation function:

$$R(z) = \max(0, z) \quad (1)$$

The last fully connected layer has 2 units, as the number of classes we defined, and it is activated by a Softmax activation:

$$\sigma(x)_j = \frac{e^{z_j}}{\sum_{M=1}^M e^{z_k}} \text{ for } j = 1, \dots, M \text{ and } z \in R \quad (2)$$

where M is the output size is the number of scalar values in the model output. As loss function optimization, we used a stochastic gradient descent method based on an adaptive

Fig. 1. CNN architecture.

estimation of first order and second-order moments (Adam), a method for problems with very noisy and/or sparse gradients [32]. Sparse Categorical Crossentropy (SCC) function is used as a loss function, which is an integer-based version of the Categorical Crossentropy function:

$$Loss = - \sum_{i=1}^M y_i \cdot \log \hat{y}_i \quad (3)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the i -th scalar value in the model output, y_i is the corresponding target value. The SCC function computes the cross-entropy loss between the labels and predictions providing labels as integers [33]. The CNN is implemented using the Google's library TensorFlow [34]. Furthermore, many augmentation techniques are applied on the dataset, such as vertical and horizontal *Random Flip*, *Random Rotation*, *Random Zoom*, and *Random Translation*. Those are chosen considering that flipping, rotating, zooming, and translating a satellite landslide image results in new images of landslides with a possible real dimension and orientation. The trained model is used to predict classes on a labeled test dataset composed of images with the same number and type of bands of the training dataset. The output contains two classes, and accuracy (4), precision (5), recall (6), and F1-score (7) are calculated using these values according to the following formulas, where TP, TN, FP, and FN are true and false positives and negatives, respectively.

$$Accuracy : a = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + FP + TN + FN)} \quad (4)$$

$$Precision : p = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)} \quad (5)$$

$$Recall : r = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} \quad (6)$$

$$F1 - score : f = 2 \frac{(p \cdot r)}{(p + r)} \quad (7)$$

C. Object Detection

The study area is analyzed through the sliding window [35] method to detect landslides. The step of the window is 2 pixels. Patches are extracted with 25 x 25 pixels resolution and then resampled to match the input size of the network.

III. RESULTS

We trained each model for the optimal number of epochs and

TABLE IV
ACCURACY, PRECISION AND RECALL OF THE CNN TESTED ON THE EIGHT
IMBALANCED TEST SETS

Dataset Name	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)
RGB	98.96	93.41	99.99	96.59
SSD	73.58	33.13	56.12	41.67
SSS	92.79	72.95	90.81	80.91
BAD	91.86	68.18	93.75	78.95
BAS	95.59	83.65	90.62	87.00
HHH	90.52	67.20	84.85	75.00
BAA	95.77	83.04	93.94	88.15
BAC	92.35	69.85	95.96	80.85
BAH	82.74	49.23	96.97	65.31

using the best learning rate that fitted each specific problem. Table IV shows the results for different datasets. The metrics are shown for imbalanced test sets to reflect the final detection results. As expected, the model trained and tested on RGB optical images performs well, achieving the best results. Focusing on SAR-based datasets, the BAS and BAA achieved the highest overall accuracies and F-scores. Furthermore, although the BAH achieved the best recall (96.97%), precision was lower than 50%. The two datasets enclosing the slope as a third band, SSS and BAS, although achieved similar accuracies (beyond 90%), the SSS show a low precision (72.95%), revealing the multi-temporal as the most reliable information to discriminate landslides. The same principle is valid for the SSD and BAS datasets. Moreover, considering the HHH and the BAA, results show that the VV polarization is more discriminating to detect landslides than the VH. More generally, precision is the most critical value for this specific case, achieving in just two cases a value beyond the 80% (BAA, BAS). To accomplish a visual evaluation of the predictions of the best models trained in this study (RGB and BAA), we analyzed the entire study area through the process explained in Section III. The maps created (Fig. 2) are shown along with the shapefile of the pre-mapped landslides (yellow) and a red polygon in correspondence to the patches predicted as *Landslide* with more than 90% probability and less than 20% overlap between two contiguous positive patches. From a visual analysis of the two images, it is noticeable how predictions on the BAA dataset are close to the RGB's. In some areas, due to the shadowing effect, landslides are missed from the SAR-based model. Anyway, encouraging is that landslides are localized also in foreshortening and layover areas.

The time spent by the model to classify 1,130,612 patches is 111 seconds. All experiments were executed on a Mac-OS operating system computer with a 2.2 GHz Intel Core i7 with 6 cores, a 256 GB SSD for quick access to applications and datasets, and RAM 16 Gb.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this letter, we analyzed and discussed various combinations of SAR imagery and topographic factors and we proposed a DL-based method for landslide detection to locate landslides in a short time, also during the night and in presence of cloud cover. Moreover, all the data exploited are open-source and

Fig. 2. Predictions on the RGB and BAA datasets (Red boxes are the model predictions while yellow polygons are the landslide inventory).

available in almost all parts of the globe. The results achieved so far are promising and suggest that SAR Sentinel-1 images and deep learning models may be a reliable combination for rapidly locating landslides. SAR images permit to obtain information regarding landslides also when optical imagery is unusable or not available because of a dense cloud cover. As for the specific case study, the optical data would have been useless in an operational emergency mapping, as the first clear optical image was available more than a month after the multiple landslide event. Therefore, the SAR-based method has relevant benefits in terms of emergency management and civil

protection operations, such as significantly decreasing the time delay in the emergency response in various scenarios by increasing the quality of hazard mapping and risk assessments. Furthermore, due to the high classification velocity, the model could be easily employed for real-time monitoring.

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